

REPOPSI

Student assistants trainings on the project

TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536.

The funding was awarded through the [RDA Open Call mechanism](#) based on evaluations of external, independent experts.

First training agenda (2022-11-22)

- | | | |
|----|--|-------------|
| 1. | Getting to know each other | 18:00-18:10 |
| 2. | REPOPSI 101 | 18:10-18:20 |
| 3. | REPOPSI structure & contents;
current ways to search REPOPSI
(focus on Open Science Framework) | 18:20-18:40 |
| 4. | Understanding the Creative Commons licence | 18:40-18:45 |
| 5. | REPOPSI Contribution form
(focus on understanding all of the fields) | 18:45-19:05 |
| 6. | About the project in short & next steps | 19:05-19:15 |
| 7. | Questions, dilemmas, observations, party time | 19:15-19:30 |

First training screenshot

Second training agenda (2022-12-12)

1. [E-Theses](#) (step-by-step instructions for searching the system; workload division; extracting basic thesis information; documenting irrelevant theses) 15:00-15:25
 2. Working Sheet (step-by-step instructions for filling in the Google Sheet for documenting relevant theses and the extracted instruments) 15:25-15:45
 3. Possible dilemmas (e.g. which instruments should be extracted and which should not; contacting thesis creators; specific instructions for the REPOPSI contribution form) 15:45-15:55
 4. Timeline and other procedures 15:55-16:05
 5. Student assistants' input (e.g. regarding the timeline, whether any of the steps can be made more efficient) 16:05-16:20
 6. Next steps, admin 16:20-16:30
-

Second training screenshot

REPOPSI

**Treninzi za studente saradnike
na projektu**

**TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of
an open repository for research
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Agenda prvog treninga (2022-11-22)

1. Pozdravljanje i upoznavanje 18.00-18.10
2. **Lična karta REPOPSI-ja** 18.10-18.20
3. Struktura i sadržaj REPOPSI-ja; 18.20-18.40
trenutni načini pretraživanja REPOPSI-ja
(fokus na Open Science Framework-u)
4. Razumevanje Creative Commons licence 18.40-18.45
5. Obrazac za doprinošenje REPOPSI-ju 18.45-19.05
(fokus na razumevanju svih delova)
6. Kratko o projektu i daljim koracima 19.05-19.15
7. Pitanja, dileme, zapažanja, slavlje 19.15-19.30

Lična karta REPOPSI-ja

osf.io/5zb8p

Kolekcija psiholoških instrumenata (stavki, skala, upitnika, testova,...) sa otvorenim pristupom

Prvi centralizovani repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata koji su prevedeni na srpski ili prilagođeni za srpsku populaciju ili koje su razvili naučnici iz Srbije

Trenutno omogućava pristup ka **178** instrumenata

I make a lot of mistakes because I don't think before I act.

Strongly
Disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly
Agree

Pravim mnogo grešaka, jer ne razmislim pre no što nešto uradim.

Potpuno
netačno

Uglavnom
netačno

Nisam
siguran

Uglavnom
tačno

Potpuno
tačno

Lična karta REPOPSI-ja

osf.io/5zb8p

Osnovali su ga i održavaju studenti i istraživači Laboratorije za istraživanje individualnih razlika Filozofskog fakulteta Univerziteta u Beogradu

I članovi drugih institucija mogu da pošalju svoje instrumente/prevode

Podrжан na platformi Open Science Framework (OSF)

Nije potreban OSF nalog da bi se koristio REPOPSI

lira.f.bg.ac.rs

osf.io

REPOPSI osf.io/5zb8p

Zašto?

Ušteda resursa za prevođenje/adaptaciju

Lakše nalaženje i ponovno korišćenje postojećih prevoda/adaptacija i originalnih instrumenata

Povećanje vidljivosti instrumenata naših istraživača

Za šta?

Lokalni i internacionalni kolaborativni projekti

Podučavanje psihometriji

Otvaranje alatki radi transparentnijeg i ponovljivijeg istraživačkog procesa (naučni članci, teze)

Za koga?

Za lokalne i strane naučnike (92/178 instrumenata dostupno i na srpskom i na engleskom)

Za istraživače, kliničare, nastavnike

Za studente

Rast broja doprinosa REPOPSI-ju, mart 2020. – oktobar 2022.

Agenda prvog treninga (2022-11-22)

- | | | |
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trenutni načini pretraživanja REPOPSI-ja
(fokus na Open Science Framework-u) | 18.20-18.40 |
| 4. | Razumevanje Creative Commons licence | 18.40-18.45 |
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OSF projekat

Demonstracija

Domaći:
Otvorite svoj
OSF nalog

Glavni delovi OSF projekta, osf.io/5zb8p

Wiki stranica na srpskom,
osf.io/5zb8p/wiki/srpski

Glavni delovi OSF komponente,
primer: osf.io/ft9kz

- ODT i PDF fajlovi sa instrumentom
- fajlovi sa sintaksom
- pregled i preuzimanje fajlova

Repository of psychological instruments in Serbian [Repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata na srpskom jeziku] (REPOPSI)

Contributors: Aleksandra Lazić, Lili Lazarevic, Iris Zezelj, Danka Purić, Marija Petrović, Mia Medojevic, Ana Ivanov, Jovan Ivanović

Date created: 2019-10-04 06:42 PM | Last Updated: 2022-09-29 10:19 PM

Identifier: DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P

Category: Project

Description: REPOPSI is a collection of psychological measures, scales, tests, and other research instruments in Serbian. REPOPSI is maintained by researchers at the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences (LIRA) at the Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade. REPOPSI contains 178 records; 92 instruments are available in both Serbian and English (last update September 16, 2022). Search the repository: <https://tinyurl.com/repopsi>

REPOPSI je kolekcija psiholoških mera, skala, testova i drugih istraživačkih instrumenata na srpskom jeziku. REPOPSI održavaju istraživači i istraživačice Laboratorije za istraživanje individualnih razlika (LIRA) Filozofskog fakulteta Univerziteta u Beogradu. REPOPSI sadrži 178 zapisa; 92 instrumenta su dostupna i na srpskom i na engleskom (zanovljeno 16. septembra 2022.). Pretražite repozitorijum: <https://tinyurl.com/repopsi>

License: Other

Wiki

Learn how to use and contribute to this Repository. [Pristupite ovoj strani na srpskom.]

The REPOPSI was launched on March 6, 2020 to provide a repository for open-access psychological measures, scales, tests, and other research instruments in Serbian. The REPOPSI is maintained by researchers at the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences (LIRA) at the Faculty of Philosophy, Universit...

[Read More](#)

Files

Citation

Components

[Non-adherence to Official Medical Recommendations Practices - NAR-12](#)

Petrović, Lazić, Lazarevic & 5 more

[Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicine Practices - TCAM-22](#)

Lazić, Lazarevic, Zezelj & 5 more

[Disintegration Scale - DELTA9](#)

Lazić, Lazarevic, Zezelj & 1 more

Repository of psychological instruments in Serbian
[Repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata na srpskom
jeziku] (REPOPSI) /

824.8KB

Public

3

Rational-Experiential Multimodal Inventory - REIm | REIm-13

Contributors: Aleksandra Lazić, Lili Lazarevic, Iris Zezelj, Danka Purić

Date created: 2020-03-04 01:52 PM | Last Updated: 2022-09-29 10:19 PM

Identifier: DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/FT9KZ

Category: Methods and Measures

License: *Other*

Files

Q Filter

Name ^ v	Modified ^ v
Rational-Experiential Multimodal Inventory - REIm REIm-13	
- OSF Storage (Germany - Frankfurt)	
reim13_eng_srp.odt	2022-04-08 08:19 PM
reim13_eng_srp.pdf	2022-04-08 08:19 PM
reim13_syntax.sps	2021-03-25 12:48 PM
reim_eng_srp.odt	2022-04-08 08:22 PM
reim_eng_srp.pdf	2022-04-08 08:19 PM
reim_syntax.sps	2021-03-25 12:48 PM

Citation

Tags

experiential intuition rational thinking style

Recent Activity

Aleksandra Lazić created external identifier(s) doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/FT9KZ on Rational-Experiential Multimodal Inventory - REIm | REIm-13

2022-04-09 07:44 PM

Aleksandra Lazić updated file reim_eng_srp.odt in OSF Storage in Rational-Experiential Multimodal Inventory - REIm | REIm-13

Title in English.	Oxford Utilitarianism Scale
Varying form of the title - translation.	Oksfordrska skala utilitarizma
Varying form of the title - abbreviation.	OUS
Version.	9-item
License.	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0
Original publisher.	
Local publisher.	
Funding projects, sponsoring agencies/individuals, or contractual arrangements.	
Abstract.	Oxford Utilitarianism Scale dissociates individual differences in the negative and positive dimensions of utilitarianism thinking. It consists of 9 items in two subscales - Impartial Beneficence (5 items) and Instrumental Harm (4 items). Participants rate how much they agree or disagree with the statements.
Keywords.	utilitarianism, moral psychology, moral dilemmas
Available languages.	srp; eng
Contact person.	Purić, Danka; Jokić, Biljana
Contact email address.	dpuric@f.bg.ac.rs; jokic.bi@gmail.com
Citation of the original instrument.	Kahane, G., Everett, J., Earp, B., Caviola, L., Faber, M., & Savulescu, J. (2017). Beyond sacrificial harm: A two-dimensional model of utilitarian psychology. <i>Psychological Review</i> , 125(2), pp.131-164.
Source of the original instrument.	https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000093
Author of the original instrument.	Kahane, Guy; Everett, Jim; Earp, Brian; Caviola, Lucius; Faber, Nadira; Crockett, Molly; Savulescu, Julian
Date of creation of the original instrument.	2017
Citation of the translation/adaptation.	Bago, B., Aczel, B., Kekecs, Z., P., Kovacs, M., Nagy, T.,...Chartier, C.R. (2019). Moral thinking across the world: Exploring the influence of personal force and intention in moral dilemma judgements. <i>PsyArXiv Preprints</i> , pp.1-21.
Source of the translation/adaptation.	https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/9uaqm
Author of the translation/adaptation.	Lazarević, Ljiljana; Bogojević, Srđan; Žeželj, Iris; Purić, Danka; Jokić, Biljana
Date of creation of the translation/adaptation.	2020
Additional notes.	

podaci o instrumentu

podaci o citiranju

Instrument in full – Translation

Language.	srp
Instructions for participants.	Ispitanici procenjuju koliko se slažu, odnosno ne slažu sa tvrdnjama.
Response scale.	7-stepena Likertova skala; 1 - Uopšte se ne slažem, 7 - potpuno se slažem
Items.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ako je jedini način da se spasi život druge osobe u hitnim slučajevima taj da se žrtvuje sopstvena noga, onda je moralni zahtev da se načini takva žrtva. 2. Moralno je ispravno da se povredi nevina osoba ako je to povređivanje neophodno sredstvo za pomoć nekim nevinim ljudima. 3. Sa moralne tačke gledišta, treba da se osećamo obaveznim da damo jedan od svojih bubrega osobi sa oštećenim bubrezima, pošto nam nisu potrebna dva bubrega da preživimo, nego samo jedan zdrav.
Scoring keys.	Računaju se prosečni skorovi za obe subskele. Ažetina čine subskalu Nepristrasnog dobroćinstva, a ažetemi 2, 4, 6, i 8 čine subskalu Instrumentalne štete.
Instructions for administrators.	
Additional notes.	

uputstvo za ispitanike

stavke

uputstvo za zadavače

Pretraživanje REPOPSI-ja

Demonstracija

3 izvora popisa instrumenata i gde ih naći:

- tinyurl.com/repopsi (Google Sheet)
- osf.io/2j7y8 (XLSX fajl)
- osf.io/mxrc2 (CSV fajl)

Pretraga u Google Sheet-u i na OSF-u

Pretraga u fajlu koji je preuzet na računar

Korisna polja u popisu

Title in English/Serbian | Abbreviation | Abstract | Keywords |

Available languages | Instrument availability | Link to instrument in the Repository

REPOPSI
Repository of psychological instruments in Serbian [Repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata na srpskom jeziku]

The list of all of the instruments in the REPOPSI, with direct links to instruments. [Spisak svih instrumenata u REPOPSI-ju, sa direktnim linkovima ka instrumentima.]

Landing page [Glavna strana] <https://osf.io/5zb8p/>

Please read <https://osf.io/5zb8p/wiki/home/>

Molimo da pročitate <https://osf.io/5zb8p/wiki/srpski/>

Terms of use [Uslov korišćenja] The instruments available in full in REPOPSI may be used without permission for noncommercial clinical, research, and educational purposes provided you cite instrument authors (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0). [Instrumenti u celini dostupni u REPOPSI-ju mogu da se koriste u nekomercijalne kliničke, istraživačke i edukativne svrhe, bez potrebe da se traži dozvola, pod uslovom da se citiraju autori instrumenata (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0).]

Contribute [Doprinesite] Please email the [Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences](mailto:lira@f.bg.ac.rs) at lira@f.bg.ac.rs. We will inform you about the necessary steps. [Molimo kontaktirajte [Laboratoriju za istraživanje individualnih razlika](mailto:lira@f.bg.ac.rs) na lira@f.bg.ac.rs. Tada ćemo vas obavestiti o daljim koracima.]

	Title in English.	Title in Serbian.	Abbreviation.	Version.	License.	Original publisher.	Local publisher.	Funding.	Abstract.	Keywords.	Available languages.	Contact person.	Contact email address.	
11	5C Antecedents of Vaccination Scale	Skala 5C prediktora vakcinacije	5C	long form; short form	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0				The 5C scale measures vaccine hesitancy.	va	srp			
12	7C Scale of Vaccination Readiness	Skala 7C spremnosti na vakcinisanje	7C	adult; long form	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0				The 7C scale measures vaccination readiness.	srp		Lazić, Aleksandr	aleksand	
13	Actively Open-Minded Thinking Scale	Skala verovanja o aktivnom mišljenju otvorenog uma	AOT	revised; short form	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					actively open-minded	eng, srp	Damnjanović, Ka	kdamnjan	
14	Adherence to COVID-19 Guidelines	Pridržavanje mera tokom COVID-19 pandemije	RHB		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0				Adherence to COVID-19	CC recommended health	srp; eng			
15	Adolescent Invulnerability Scale	Skala adolescentske neranjivosti	AIS		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0				The Adolescent Invulnerability Scale	adolescents, physical	srp; eng	Dojčinović, Sara	sara.dojc	
16	Adult Crying Inventory	Inventar za procenu sklonosti ka plakanju za odrasle	ACI		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0				The 24-item section of the adult crying, emotion	srp		Lazarević, Ljiljana	ljiljana.la	
17	Affective Neuroscience Personality Scales	Skale ličnosti zasnovane na afektivnoj neuronauci	ANPS		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					personality, affective	srp	Knezević, Goran		
18	Ambivalent Sexism Inventory	Skala ambivalentnog seksizma	ASI	short form	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					ambivalent sexism	h	eng, srp		
19	Amoralism Scale	Skala amoralnosti	AMRL9	54-item	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					amoralism, moral	bel	srp	Knezević, Goran	gknezevi
20	Anchoring Effect Tasks	Zadaci za merenja efekta ukotvljavanja	AE		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0				In the initial phase of the anchoring effect,	cog	srp; eng	Teovanović, Pred	teovanovi	
21	Assessment Checklist for Qualities Relevant in Rhythmic Cognition	Ček-lista za procenu kvaliteta relevantnih za bavljenje ritmičkim kognitivnim zadacima	RG23							rhythmic gymnastics	srp	Damnjanović, Ka	kdamnjan	
22	Assessment of Sadistic Personality	Procena sadističke ličnosti	ASP		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					sadism, dark triad	di	srp	Dinic, Bojana	bojana.di
23	Attitudes on Academic Honesty	Stavovi prema akademskom poštenju	ATTAH		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					academic honesty	a	srp		
24	Attitudes on Higher Education	Stavovi prema visokom obrazovanju	ATTHER		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					higher education	nee	srp		
25	Balanced Inventory of Desirable Responding	Balansirani inventar socijalno poželjnog odgovaranja	BIDR						Two subscales: the desirable responding	eng, srp		Knezević, Goran	gknezevi	
26	Base Rate Neglect Tasks	Zadaci za merenje sklonosti zanemarivanja osnovne verovatnoće	BRN		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0				For each of the 10 items, the base rate neglect	co	srp	Teovanović, Pred	teovanovi	
27	Belief in a Competitive Jungle World Scale	Verovanja u kompetitivnu džunglu	BCJWS		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					beliefs, worldview	co	eng, srp	Knezević, Goran	gknezevi
28	Belief in a Dangerous World Scale	Verovanja u opasan svet	BDWS		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					beliefs, worldview	da	eng, srp	Knezević, Goran	gknezevi
29	Belief in a Just World Scale	Skala verovanja u pravedan svet	BJWS		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0					beliefs, worldview	jus	eng, srp	Lazarević, Ljiljana	ljiljana.la
30	Belief in COVID-19 Conspiracy Theories Scale	Skala verovanja u COVID-19 teorije zavere	TZCOV		CC BY-NC-SA 4.0				Belief in COVID-19 conspiracy theories	beliefs, co	srp; eng			

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(fokus na Open Science Framework-u) | 18.20-18.40 |
| 4. | Razumevanje Creative Commons licence | 18.40-18.45 |
| 5. | Obrazac za doprinošenje REPOPSI-ju
(fokus na razumevanju svih delova) | 18.45-19.05 |
| 6. | Kratko o projektu i daljim koracima | 19.05-19.15 |
| 7. | Pitanja, dileme, zapažanja, slavlje | 19.15-19.30 |

Korišćenje instrumenata dostupnih u celini u REPOPSI-ju

- BY** – U obavezi ste da navedete autora dela
- NC** – Nije dozvoljeno korišćenje u komercijalne svrhe
- SA** – Ako menjate delo, u obavezi ste da ga delite pod istom licencom

Autorstvo-Nekomercijalno-Deliti pod istim uslovima 4.0 međunarodna licenca, creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/deed.sr_LATN

Možete da koristite instrumente u nekomercijalne kliničke, istraživačke i obrazovne svrhe, pod uslovom da citirate autore instrumenta i adaptacije/prevoda

Agenda prvog treninga (2022-11-22)

- | | | |
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Doprinošenje REPOPSI-ju

Demonstracija

Prolazak kroz popunjen obrazac za originalni instrument (objavljen rad)

Prolazak kroz popunjen obrazac za prevedeni instrument (neobjavljen rad)

Scriberia

Agenda prvog treninga (2022-11-22)

- | | | |
|----|--|-------------|
| 1. | Pozdravljanje i upoznavanje | 18.00-18.10 |
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TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs

Project funded by an RDA/EOSC Future Cross-disciplinary Science Adoption €50.000 Grant

WP1: Improving the TRUSTworthiness and FAIRness of the Repository

WP2: Disseminating the activities

WP3: Improving the completeness of the data in the Repository

Core team members: Aleksandra Lazić, Ljiljana Lazarević, Danka Purić, Iris Žeželj, & Obrad Vučkovic

Kicks off November 2022

Agenda prvog treninga (2022-11-22)

- | | | |
|----|---|-------------|
| 1. | Pozdravljanje i upoznavanje | 18.00-18.10 |
| 2. | Lična karta REPOPSI-ja | 18.10-18.20 |
| 3. | Trenutna struktura i sadržaj REPOPSI-ja;
trenutni načini pretraživanja REPOPSI-ja
(fokus na Open Science Framework-u) | 18.20-18.40 |
| 4. | Razumevanje Creative Commons licence | 18.40-18.45 |
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(fokus na razumevanju svih delova) | 18.45-19.05 |
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Hvala!

Pratite #REPOPSI

**Laboratorija za istraživanje
individualnih razlika**

Twitter: [@LiraLab_Bgd](https://twitter.com/LiraLab_Bgd)

Facebook: [LiraLab.Bgd](https://www.facebook.com/LiraLab.Bgd)

LinkedIn: [company/lira-lab-bgd](https://www.linkedin.com/company/lira-lab-bgd)

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